

Estimation of Small Quantities of Arsenic in Medicolegal Cases.

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In medicolegal investigations of arsenic poisoning cases, it is of importance to determine the quantity of arsenic in viscera and other articles, submitted for analysis.

In our experience, the destruction of organic matter is best done by slightly modified Bang's method (*Analyst*, 1925, 50, 5). We also tried the destruction of organic matter by Fresenius-Babo method ("Royal Commission on Arsenical Poisoning, Minutes on Evidence and Appendices," 1903, XI, 223), invariably a loss of arsenic due to volatilisation during the process of removing nitric acid, however, carefully it is done.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The process adopted by us is as follows. About 50 g. of the substance were taken in a silica Kjeldahl flask; spirit (if used as preservative), or water, if present, should first be removed before putting the substance into the flask. 8.0 ml. of strong H_2SO_4 were added, followed by 2.0 ml. of strong HNO_3 . The flask was then gently heated on a wire gauze, and HNO_3 was dripped into the flask from a separating funnel with a bent stem. In about 5 to 6 hours' time the digestion was complete, and a clear liquid was obtained. The major portion of the nitric acid remaining in the liquid was got rid of by heating it until white fumes appeared. The last traces of the nitric acid were removed by boiling the liquid in the flask with 10 ml. of saturated ammonium oxalate or saturated urea solution. We have found that without this treatment traces of HNO_3 remain in the liquid, which interfere with the estimation of arsenic.

When the quantity of arsenic is small, two methods for its determination are applicable, viz., the Gutzeit and the Marsh-Berzelious method. We find it more convenient to adopt the electrolytic Marsh-Berzelious method ("Royal Commission Report on Arsenical Poisoning," 1903, p. 4) using platinum electrodes with certain modifications as stated below.

The platinum gauze was discarded and the tube was heated directly by putting it just above the reducing zone of the flame. The gas pressure, which is indicated by a manometer having one end open and the other connected to the gas conducting tube and containing some coloured water, was adjusted by a pinch-cock. A difference of one inch in the two arms of the manometer was maintained. The temperature of the water in the cooling bath was not allowed to rise above 10° . As the atmospheric shade temperature in Agra generally varies from 45° to 2° during the year, the following device was employed to maintain the required temperature of the bath which was kept fed with ice. In summer when the atmospheric temperature is pretty high, the water in the bath was protected from being heated up by the air temperature, by covering the outside walls and the top of the bath, except the portion occupied by the electrolytic glass cell, with asbestos sheets. In winter the heat developed within the electrolytic cell was allowed to radiate into the cool outside atmosphere by removing the asbestos sheets. The Marsh's tube in which the mirror was formed was placed on a small circular asbestos disc having a hole at the centre for the flame and resting on the chimney of the gas burner in order to prevent heat being conducted through the wall of the chimney with radiation into the atmosphere. If the heat be not sufficient, the arsenuretted hydrogen is not completely decomposed. It is also necessary in the hot weather of Agra to prevent the overheating of the part of the tube where the arsenic is to deposit. This is done by placing an asbestos screen vertically between the chimney of the burner and the part of the tube where the arsenic mirror is to form, the tube passing through a hole in the asbestos screen.

It is extremely important that before introducing the solution, obtained after destruction of the organic matter into the Marsh's apparatus, the arsenic contained in it should be reduced completely into the arsenious state. We found that sulphurous acid is not satisfactory for this purpose. The reduction of arsenic by it is not only incomplete, but uncertain in extent. Reduction with a solution of arsenic was accomplished by digesting the solution on a water-bath with a mixture of pyrogallie acid solution and sulphurous acid. This was done with respect of each portion of the solution introduced into the Marsh's apparatus and immediately before starting the test, ensuring at the same time that no excess of sulphurous acid remained in the solution. Unless the reduction of arsenic be done immediately before the test, some of the reduced arsenic is again transformed into its higher state of oxidation. The qualities of the reagents used by us were 2.0 c.c. of 0.5% pyrogallie acid solution and 4.0 c.c. of sulphurous acid. By this process quite good results were obtained, without previous distillation of the solution as has been recommended in the case of dyestuffs (*Analyst*, 1930, 55, 103). It was also found unnecessary to prepare the standard arsenic solution by treatment of the same kind of material as under examination after adding to it a known quantity of As_2O_3 as recommended by some authorities (Royal Commission Report on Arsenic Poisoning, 1903, p. 10). We prepared the standard solution by directly dissolving arsenious acid.

The following table shows the advantage of reducing the arsenic in the solution for test into arsenious state by a mixture of pyrogallie and sulphuric acids in the manner stated above.

Nature of substance to which a weighed quantity of As_2O_3 added and the soln. for test prepared after destruction of the organic matter by the modified Bang's method.	The entire liquid after digestion reduced with H_2SO_4 , made up to a known volume and further diluted, H_2SO_4 acid, just before the test if necessary for Marsh's test.	Only the portion introduced into the Marsh's apparatus reduced with pyrogallic and sulphurous acids, just before the test.	Amt. of As_2O_3 taken in the electrolytic apparatus, from the soln. to tus.	The standard As_2O_3 mirror with which the mirror apparatus, from the soln. to tus, match.	Amt. of As_2O_3 taken in the electrolytic apparatus, from the soln. to tus.	The standard As_2O_3 mirror with which the mirror apparatus, from the soln. to tus, match.
Coat's viscera	0.03 mg.	0.007 mg.	0.0036 mg.	0.002 mg.	0.0036 ni.g.	0.004 mg.
"	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.005	0.006	0.006
"	0.016	0.006	0.0064	0.004	0.0064	0.006
"	0.020	0.006	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.006
"	0.013	0.006	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.004
Arsenic-free human stomach	0.021	0.006	0.0062	0.003	0.0062	0.006

The chemicals used in the test were all free from arsenic

All the standard mirrors were prepared from the same stock solution, which before introduction into the electrolytic apparatus was treated with a mixture of pyrogallic and sulphurous acid solutions.